

Synthesis, spectral characterization and *in vitro* antifungal activity of lanthanum(III) and praseodymium(III) complexes with Schiff bases derived from 5-substituted-4-amino-5-hydrazino-1,2,4-triazoles and isatin

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Abstract : The new lanthanum(III) and praseodymium(III) complexes of the general formula $[\text{LnCl}(\text{L})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ ($\text{Ln} = \text{La}^{\text{III}}$ or Pr^{III} ; $\text{H}_2\text{L} =$ Schiff bases derived from 3-substituted-4-amino-5-hydrazino-1,2,4-triazoles and isatin) have been prepared. The complexes have been characterized by elemental analyses, molecular weight by FAB-mass, thermogravimetry, electrical conductance, magnetic moment and spectral (electronic, infrared, far-infrared, ^1H NMR and ^{13}C NMR) data. The ligands and all prepared complexes were assayed for antifungal (*Aspergillus niger* and *Helminthosporium oryzae*) activities. The activities have been correlated with the structures of the complexes.

Keywords : Lanthanum(III), praseodymium(III), Schiff bases, IR, NMR, fungicidal activity.

Introduction

1,2,4-Triazoles and their derivatives are associated with various biological activities; such as anticonvulsant, antifungal, anticancer, anti-inflammatory and antibacterial properties¹⁻⁷. Several compounds containing this 1,2,4-triazole rings are well known for drugs¹. 1,2,4-Triazoles containing amino groups are also importance for obtaining various Schiff base derivatives with well-known antimicrobial properties⁸⁻¹⁰. Schiff base hydrazone ligands containing 1,2,4-triazole nucleus have attracted great and growing interest in chemistry and biology due to their facile synthesis and wide applications¹¹⁻¹⁴. Few papers have also appeared on coordination behaviors of such ligands towards transition metal ion¹⁵⁻¹⁷. The coordination behaviour of such ligands depends upon the nature of metal ion, nature of the substituent of the ligand and the pH of the medium. These ligands have donor sites with the ONNO sequences and varied coordinating abilities. This nature of ligands has attributed our attention and aroused our interest in elucidating the structures of La^{III} and Pr^{III} complexes with these Schiff bases, as there is scant information on these complexes of the ligands.

In this article we report the synthesis, characterization and biological activities of lanthanum(III) and praseodymium(III) derivatives with Schiff bases derived from 3-substituted-4-amino-5-hydrazino-1,2,4-triazole and isatin.

Experimental

The reagent and solvent were analytical grade; lanthanum(III) chloride and praseodymium(III) chloride were purchased from B.D.H. The ligands were prepared by the condensation of isatin with appropriate triazole as reported in literature¹⁸.

The details of analytical methods and physical measurements were the same as described earlier¹⁹.

Preparation of complexes :

An ethanolic solution (20 cm³) of the appropriate metal chloride (0.01 mol; ~2.5 g) was added dropwise to an ethanolic solution (20 cm³) of the appropriate Schiff base (0.01 mol) containing a few drops of HCl. The resulting mixture was boiled under reflux for 12-17 h. Brown coloured precipitate were separated which were filtered, washed with ether and finally dried *in vacuo*.

The details of the reaction along with the analytical data of the products were given in Table 1.

Table 1. Characterization data of lanthanum(III) and praseodymium(III) complexes

Reactants (molar ratio)	Refluxing time (h)	Product Yield (%)	Colour	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)			
				C	H	N	Ln
LaCl ₃ + IPHTH ₂ (1 : 1)	15	[La(IPHT)Cl(H ₂ O)] (52)	Light brown	45.0 (45.1)	2.4 (2.5)	17.5 (17.5)	21.5 (21.7)
PrCl ₃ + IPHTH ₂ (1 : 1)	12	[Pr(IPHT)Cl(H ₂ O)] (64)	Dark brown	44.8 (45.0)	2.5 (2.5)	17.3 (17.5)	21.8 (22.0)
LaCl ₃ + IPNHTH ₂ (1 : 1)	10	[La(IPNHT)Cl(H ₂ O)] (65)	Light brown	42.0 (42.2)	2.1 (2.2)	18.2 (18.4)	20.2 (20.3)
PrCl ₃ + IPNHTH ₂ (1 : 1)	13	[Pr(IPNHT)Cl(H ₂ O)] (63)	Light brown	41.9 (42.0)	2.2 (2.2)	18.2 (18.4)	20.4 (20.6)
LaCl ₃ + IPCHTH ₂ (1 : 1)	12	[La(IPCHT)Cl(H ₂ O)] (59)	Light brown	42.6 (42.8)	2.2 (2.3)	16.5 (16.6)	20.5 (20.6)
PrCl ₃ + IPCHTH ₂ (1 : 1)	16	[Pr(IPCHT)Cl(H ₂ O)] (55)	Dark brown	42.5 (42.7)	2.1 (2.2)	16.6 (16.6)	20.7 (20.9)
LaCl ₃ + IOCHTH ₂ (1 : 1)	15	[La(IOCHT)Cl(H ₂ O)] (61)	Dark brown	42.7 (42.8)	2.2 (2.3)	16.5 (16.6)	20.6 (20.6)
PrCl ₃ + IOCHTH ₂ (1 : 1)	17	[Pr(IOCHT)Cl(H ₂ O)] (60)	Light brown	42.6 (42.7)	2.2 (2.2)	16.4 (16.6)	20.8 (20.9)

Results and discussion

The condensation of 3-(phenyl/2-chlorophenyl/4-chlorophenyl/4-nitrophenyl)-3-amino-5-hydrazino-1,2,4-triazoles with isatin in ethanol containing a few drops of concentrated hydrochloric acid gives rise to Schiff base (1) as shown in Scheme 1.

A systematic study of reaction of the lanthanum(III) and praseodymium(III) chloride with Schiff bases (H₂L) derived from 3-(phenyl/2-chlorophenyl/4-chlorophenyl/4-nitrophenyl)-4-amino-5-hydrazino-1,2,4-triazoles (molar ratio 1 : 1) in ethanol may be represented by the following equation :

The complexes are insoluble in common organic solvents, but partially soluble in DMF and DMSO. The presence of coordinated water molecule is inferred from thermogravimetric analysis, which indicates loss of two water molecules at 150–170 °C. The electrical conductivity measurements show that the complexes are non-electrolytes.

Magnetic moments and electronic spectra :

The lanthanum(III) complexes, as expected, have no

resultant magnetic moment, whereas the magnetic moment of praseodymium(III) complexes lie in the range of 3.56–3.60 μ_B, which shows little deviation from Van-Vleck value, i.e. 3.62 for the Pr³⁺ ion.

The electronic spectra of the paramagnetic lanthanide complexes have been the subject of recent extensive reviews²⁰⁻²³, which deal particularly with the physical and theoretical aspects. The Pr³⁺ ion has the outer configuration $4f^2 5s^2 5p^6$ and follows the Russell-Saunders L, S, J coupling scheme with a certain amount of configuration interaction. The $5s$ and $5p$ subshell have a radial dispersion, which is greater than $4f$ electrons, and, hence, shield the latter from the effect of coordinated ligands to a very large extent but not completely. Thus, the electronic spectra of Pr^{III} can be considered²⁴ as derived from the spectra of the gaseous ions by a fairly small perturbation. The perturbation can be of two general types. The first is a general nephelauxetic effect owing to the drift of ligand or $5s$, $5p$ electron density into the metal ion, slightly expanding the $4f$ subshell and reducing the $4f-4f$ interactions. The second is a crystal field splitting effect, which removes the degeneracy of the free ion levels and which can be represented with fair success by a point negative charge model having the appropriate molecular symmetry.

The spectra of La³⁺ ions are composed of closely spaced sharp lines. The group of lines is normally spread over an energy interval of several hundred cm⁻¹. These spectra arise from transitions among levels of f^n configuration. The $4f$ electrons of lanthanides are more or less protected from the influence of lattice by the polarization of $5s^2$ and $5p^6$ closed shell. The crystal field splitting effect in the La³⁺ ion is small, 200-300 cm⁻¹ at the most. Thus, to a good approximation, the levels agree well with that for the free ion.

The f^2 configuration of a free Pr³⁺ ion involves 13 energy levels. Their location is found experimentally by the analyses of the spectra for a gaseous Pr³⁺ ion. The ground terms appears to be 3H_4 . The absorption spectra of Pr³⁺ ion solution in the visible region involve four bands due to the transition from the ground level to 3P_0 , $^3P_1 + ^1I_6$, 3P_0 and 1D_2 levels. The $f-f$ transitions are weakly allowed due to some mixing of the excited state of the opposite parity into the ground state and a marked enhancement in the intensity of the band upon complexation is observed. This is due to an increase in the configuration interaction upon complexation²⁵. The Pr^{III} complexes shows bands around 16600-16780, 20400-20600, 21100-21400 and 23200-23500 cm⁻¹ corresponding to the tran-

sition from 3H_4 to 1D_2 , 3P_0 , 3P_1 and 3P_2 energy levels, respectively.

The nephelauxetic effect is quantitatively described by a nephelauxetic parameter equal to the ratio of the interelectron repulsion parameter (either Slater's integrals F_k , or Racah's parameter E^k) in the complex and in the free ion :

$$\beta = \frac{(F_k)_{\text{complex}}}{(F_k)_{\text{free ion}}} \text{ or } \bar{\beta} = \frac{(E^k)_{\text{complex}}}{(E^k)_{\text{free ion}}}$$

As the nephelauxetic effect value $(1 - \bar{\beta})$ is small in the lanthanide complex, it can be, to a fairly good approximation defined from the ratio of the wave numbers of $f-f$ transitions in the spectra of the complex and the free ion.

$$\beta \approx \frac{V_{\text{complex}}}{V_{\text{free ion}}}$$

Since, in general case, the energy levels in the lanthanide free ions are unknown the relative nephelauxetic effects $\bar{\beta}$ and are usually determined from the experimental data using the spectra of the lanthanide aqua ions as standards.

$$\bar{\beta} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{n=1}^n \frac{V_{\text{complex}}}{V_{\text{aquo}}}$$

From the mean $\bar{\beta}$ values, Sinha's covalency parameter (δ) and bonding parameter ($b^{1/2}$) are calculated using the following formulas :

$$\delta = \frac{1 - \bar{\beta}}{\bar{\beta}} \times 100 \text{ and } b^{1/2} = \left[\frac{1 - \bar{\beta}}{2} \right]^{1/2}$$

These parameters measure the amount of $4f$ -ligand mixing, i.e. covalency.

The values of the parameters $\bar{\beta}$, δ and $b^{1/2}$ of these complexes are given in Table 2. The values of β which are less than unity and the positive values of δ and $b^{1/2}$ support partial covalent nature of bonding between the metal and ligands.

IR spectra :

The infrared spectra of the ligands and their corresponding lanthanum(III) and praseodymium(III) complexes are given in Table 3. The spectra of the free Schiff bases show a medium band at *ca.* 3150 cm⁻¹ due to $\nu(\text{N-H})$, which persists almost at the same position in the com-

Table 2. Electronic spectral parameters of praseodymium(III) complexes of Schiff bases derived from 3-substituted-4-amino-5-hydrazino-1,2,4-triazoles and isatin

Complexes	$\bar{\nu}$	δ	$b^{1/2}$
[Pr(IPHT)Cl(H ₂ O)]	0.9895	1.0611	0.0724
[Pr(IPNHT)Cl(H ₂ O)]	0.9900	1.1010	0.0707
[Pr(IPCHT)Cl(H ₂ O)]	0.9882	1.1941	0.0768
[Pr(IOCHT)Cl(H ₂ O)]	0.9878	1.2350	0.0781

Thus, the infrared spectra reveal that the Schiff base ligands behave as dibasic, tetradentate ligands coordinating through two azomethine nitrogens and two enolic oxygens through deprotonation.

¹H NMR spectra :

The proton magnetic resonance spectra of the complexes of type [La(L)Cl(H₂O)] have been recorded in

Table 3. Characteristic IR spectral data of Schiff bases derived from 3-substituted-4-amino-5-hydrazino-1,2,4-triazole and their corresponding lanthanum(III) and praseodymium(III) complexes

Complex/Ligand	$\nu(\text{NH})$	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$	Phenolic $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$	$\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$	$\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$
IPHTH ₂	3150m, 3052m	1618m	1598m	1292m	-	-
IPNHT ₂	3134m, 3126m	1617m	1592m	1294m	-	-
IPCHTH ₂	3114m, 3060m	1619s	1599m	1294s	-	-
IOCHTH ₂	3150m, 3065m	1620m	1589w	1291m	-	-
[La(IPHT)Cl(H ₂ O)]	3130m	1595s	1575s	1380s	432m	324m
[Pr(IPHT)Cl(H ₂ O)]	3132m	1600s	1580m	1375s	445m	360m
[La(IPNHT)Cl(H ₂ O)]	3139w	1602m	1579m	1371m	435m	320m
[Pr(IPNHT)Cl(H ₂ O)]	3140m	1605s	1575m	1373s	440m	350m
[La(IPCHT)Cl(H ₂ O)]	3132m	1604m	1578m	1370m	430m	320m
[Pr(IPCHT)Cl(H ₂ O)]	3136w	1600s	1573m	1379m	450m	350m
[La(IOCHT)Cl(H ₂ O)]	3135m	1605s	1580m	1375s	432m	325m
[Pr(IOCHT)Cl(H ₂ O)]	3130m	1600m	1574m	1380s	445m	350m

plexes indicating the non-involvement of this group in bond formation. The ligands show one medium intensity band at *ca.* 1620 cm⁻¹ assignable²⁶ to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$, which shifts to *ca.* 1600 cm⁻¹ in the complexes. This shift in the position of $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ indicates the coordination of azomethine nitrogens to the metal. In the far IR spectra, the bands at *ca.* 430–445, 320–360 cm⁻¹ are assigned to $\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$ and $\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$ respectively. The spectra of the free Schiff bases show medium intensity band at *ca.* 1580 cm⁻¹ assignable to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ of the triazole ring which remains at the same position in the complexes indicating²⁷ the non-coordination of ring nitrogens to the metal.

In addition, the spectra of the ligands show bands at 3180 and 1680 cm⁻¹, which are assigned²⁸ to $\nu(\text{N}-\text{H})$ and $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ vibrations of isatin moiety. These bands disappear in lanthanum(III) or praseodymium(III) complexes, which may be due to enolization of keto group. This is further confirmed by the appearance of new bands at 1580 cm⁻¹ and 1520–1530 cm⁻¹ regions, assignable to newly formed $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ and $\nu(\text{NCO})$ groups. In addition, all complexes show broad band at 3400 cm⁻¹ due to $\nu(\text{OH})$ of coordinated water molecules.

deuterated dimethylsulphoxide. The different proton magnetic resonance signals are given in Table 4. The intensities of all the resonance lines were determined by planimetric integration. The spectra are complicated by coupling between various groups, but a comparison of the spectra of ligands with those of the complexes can lead to the following conclusions :

(a) The proton signals of NH group of the free Schiff bases are seen at 13.6–13.8 ppm. This signal remains almost at the same position in the complexes indicating the non-coordination of NH group during complexation.

(b) The chemical shift due to aromatic ring protons appears 7.0–7.5 ppm in the ligands which slightly shifts downfield in the complexes. This may be due to the decrease of electron density after forming the complex.

(c) The peak due to NH of isatin ring appears at 11.2 ppm in the spectra of ligands which disappears in their corresponding complexes.

(d) The free Schiff bases show a signal at 10.5 ppm due to the OH group which is absent for the correspond-

Table 4. ^1H and ^{13}C chemical shift (δ in ppm) of lanthanum(III) complexes at 25 °C

Complex	^1H			^{13}C		
	Aromatic ring	CH=N	NH	C-2	C-3	C-10
[La(IPHT)Cl(H ₂ O)]	7.15s	8.34s	13.69s	130.8	125.5	156.2
[La(IPNHT)Cl(H ₂ O)]	7.22s	3.38s	13.80s	132.5	126.4	157.6
[La(IPCHT)Cl(H ₂ O)]	7.85s	8.35s	13.78s	135.8	129.0	158.6
[La(IOCHT)Cl(H ₂ O)]	7.75–7.85m	8.22s	13.60s	133.6	127.0	160.2

ing complexes indicating the deprotonation of OH group during complex formation.

(e) The resonance due to azomethine protons appear at 8.1 ppm which undergoes downfield shift in the complexes.

^{13}C NMR :

The ^{13}C NMR spectra of [La(L)Cl(H₂O)₂] complexes were recorded in DMSO (Table 4). The ligands show amide C(2) and C(10) at δ 60.0 and 50.0, respectively. In the complexes, these signals are at significantly higher field. The significant shift in the position of C(2) (δ 130–135.8) may be due the enolization of keto group and formation of new azomethine linkage. The signal due to C(3) appear in the region (δ 125.5–129.0).

On the basis of elemental analyses, electrical conductance measurement and spectral data, the following structure (2) is tentatively proposed for [Ln(L)Cl(H₂O)₂] complexes.

(2)

Antifungal activity :

The fungicidal activity of the ligands and their corresponding [Ln(L)Cl(H₂O)] complexes in DMF were evaluated against *Aspergillus niger* and *Helminthosporium oryzae* by the agar plate technique²⁹ at concentrations of 1000, 100 and 10 ppm with triplicate determination in each case. The average percentage inhibition after 96 h

was calculated from the expression :

$$\text{Inhibition (\%)} = 100 \times C - T/C$$

where *C* is the diameter of the fungus colony in control plates and *T* is the diameter of the fungus colony in tested plates both after 96 h.

The results of the antifungal tests are recorded in Table 5. The ligands show significant activity against both species of fungi at 1000 ppm concentration. However, the activity increases upon complexation. The maximum activity was observed for complexes with ligands having chlorine at 2-position on the phenyl ring. Lanthanum(III) complexes are slightly more toxic than praseodymium(III) complexes.

Table 5. Fungicidal screening data

Complex	Fungicidal inhibition (%)					
	<i>A. niger</i>			<i>H. oryzae</i>		
	1000	100	10	1000	100	10
IPHTH ₂	59.9	50.2	44.8	52.5	44.6	40.2
[La(IPHT)Cl(H ₂ O)]	69.2	62.0	52.6	62.5	56.8	47.5
[Pr(IPHT)Cl(H ₂ O)]	66.5	59.9	50.0	58.6	52.5	42.6
IPNHTH ₂	64.2	56.0	46.8	56.5	48.2	44.6
[La(IPNHT)Cl(H ₂ O)]	72.1	68.2	57.2	64.1	60.5	52.6
[Pr(IPNHT)Cl(H ₂ O)]	69.0	61.6	51.6	59.2	55.3	48.1
IPCHTH ₂	68.2	60.6	50.2	60.2	52.6	48.2
[La(IPCHT)Cl(H ₂ O)]	74.0	71.6	59.8	68.2	62.1	57.5
[Pr(IPCHT)Cl(H ₂ O)]	70.8	68.5	55.2	64.3	58.0	51.2
IOCHTH ₂	72.6	68.0	58.8	70.8	65.6	49.8
[La(IOCHT)Cl(H ₂ O)]	78.8	74.2	64.2	77.2	70.5	56.0
[Pr(IOCHT)Cl(H ₂ O)]	76.5	70.1	61.5	75.1	67.1	53.6

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